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Unite! Challenges and Convergences Roadmap

Deliverable 2.1

Deliverable

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Author(s) – Partner(s)	G. Pellegrino (POLITO), V. Romano (POLITO), E. P. Ambrosio (POLITO), J. Wanselius (KTH), E. Bingham (AALTO), J. Perez (UPC), F. Balestra (INP GRENOBLE), L. Melo (ULISBOA), B. Koehler (TUDa)
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Introduction

WP2 will develop a common R&I agenda for the partner universities of the Unite! Alliance enabling tangible progress for the alliance, in line with Horizon Europe 2021-2027, the European Commission's priorities, such as the European Green Deal and the UN agenda 2030, as well as seamlessly integrated with the education agenda which is being developed in the complementary Erasmus+ project, which established the framework within which Unite! was born.

The R&I agenda will be translated into feasible transformation actions (action plan) and pilot actions, coherent with the policy of each partner and the open science principles and coordinated among WPs.

In order to reach this ambitious goal, the different phases of WP2 have been identified, each having a specific objective:

1. Identification of R&I (R&I) challenges and convergences of the partner universities, in line with the mission statement of the Unite! European University Alliance.
2. Setting up of the Unite! Agenda and joint action plans to create EU-level critical mass
3. Implementation of action plans and the R&I agenda

This report presents the work and output of Task 2.1: Challenges and Convergences covering the period M1-M8 to define a roadmap on compelling global challenges of common interest among the Unite! Partners through the identification of R&I challenges and convergences of the partner universities, in line with the mission statement of the Unite! European University Alliance (objective 1 above).

After a brief description of the methodology, the following sections present a review of partners R&I strategic plans, a list of stakeholders that could give input on Alliance R&I Strategic plans, a SWOT analysis, a brief overview of the EU and national funding opportunities and next steps.

Methodology

In order to reach the first objective and identify R&I challenges and convergences of the partner universities, three actions were foreseen, as agreed among the WP2 members during the proposal writing phase and confirmed during the kick-off meeting:

- Review of partners R&I strategic plans (SPs), list of stakeholders' for input on Alliance R&I SPs;
- Alignment of partners in the approach to international, EU, national and regional policies;
- Definition of a Roadmap on compelling global challenges of common interest.

The following methodology was adopted:

- A survey was set up to map the complementary strengths (and weaknesses) of the partners in the research and innovation dimension, aimed at providing an overview of R&I strategic plans of each partner.

- Ad hoc discussion on the outcome of the survey to identify common trends and goals in R&I.
- Interaction with the other WPs, and in particular with WP4, WP7 and WP9, for input from external stakeholders
- Presentation of the outcome of the survey during the WP Leader Board of June 14th, 2021, for feedback and suggestions
- SWOT analysis of the strategic plans, aimed at identifying R&I challenges and convergences
- Identification of policies and funding priorities and instruments at international, EU, national and regional policies to support and implement the future R&I challenges of the Alliance
- After the identification of challenges and convergences setting up, implementation of the Unite! Agenda and joint action plans to create EU-level critical mass.

A detailed description of the actions is reported in the following.

Review of partners R&I strategic plans

Actions:

- A questionnaire was agreed upon and filled by the partners (Annex I)
- Convergence was found, based on the questionnaire results

Output on R&I strategic plans:

- Complementary strengths (and weaknesses) of the partners in the R&I dimension. Research platforms and other research structures transversal to departments and schools exist in each partner university
- Identification of challenges and convergences among the partners: attraction of talent, share of open infrastructures, be part of a larger network, build and maintain relations, joint EU Projects, create strategic links with KICs, build on E+ Unite!
- Identification of thematic areas of common interest: Energy, Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence, Green Deal and Materials

Output on stakeholders' overview:

- input from WP4 (business), WP7 (society) and WP9 (dissemination) collected.

Alignment of partners in the approach to international, EU, national and regional R&I policies

Actions: Review of the organization of the research offices of the partners

Output: Creation of a network of contact reference persons, towards the network of Research, TT and HR offices promised as pilot project

Definition of a Roadmap on compelling global challenges of common interest

Output: The areas of common interests were identified: Energy, Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence, Green Deal and Materials

Review of R&I Strategic Plans

Strategic Plan research priorities of each university

1. POLITECNICO DI TORINO (POLITO)

The POLITO4IMPACT Strategic Plan sets the 2018 – 2024 agenda. This is inspired by the UN SDGs, the Mega-Trends reported in the OECD “STI Outlook” reports and designed with reference to the H2020 and the Horizon Europe Framework Programs. The principles of Open Science and Responsible R&I will be encouraged.

The R&I priorities are:

- Support the digitalization of research: foster synergies between digital disciplines and other fields of engineering, architecture, planning and design.
- Support multidisciplinary research. Our university will advance the organizational model adopted by the Interdepartmental Centres and will promote the evolution of their research agenda based on periodical evaluations and the identification of new strategic directions.
- Foster the integration between basic and applied research, ensuring an impactful dissemination towards industry and society.

The Strategic Plan includes investments in R&I through the creation of new labs and infrastructures and the cooperation with public and private stakeholders. The new Technology Platforms (TPs) are environments for gathering all resources and optimizing their visibility and successful exploitation. The TP pilot cases are dedicated to Manufacturing 4.0, Circular Economy, Digital Revolution, Energy Water & Climate. Mobility 3D and Urban & Territorial Regeneration are under implementation. Goals of the next years are related to digital transformation, green technologies and sustainable mobility

2. INSTITUT POLYTECHNIQUE DE GRENOBLE (INP GRENOBLE)

- Meeting new economic, environmental, and societal challenges, through our training and research
- Encourage cutting-edge research, with the ambition of providing sustainable solutions
- Spread the pioneering culture, the spirit of research, the taste for innovation, transfer and development
- Strengthen our relations with the socio-economic world to inspire, build, capitalize and disseminate the knowledge of tomorrow

- The strategic R&I orientations are proposed by the Research and Valorization Office, which includes 1 Deputy Vice-President (Europe) and 4 Scientific Directors in charge of strategic research areas, under the leadership of the Research Vice-President of Grenoble INP, the Vice-President Business and Valorization of Grenoble INP and the Vice President of Research and Innovation of University Grenoble-Alpes. Orientations are then submitted for discussion and approval by the Scientific Council before a possible discussion in the framework of the Grenoble INP Governing Board when the subject has a strong impact on the overall strategy.
- Research in INP GRENOBLE is organized in 6 poles for the 100 research labs of the University. The poles propose the scientific strategy of their scope, the major interactions between poles and the research recruitment strategy

3. UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA (UPC)

The main objective of UPC RESEARCH STRATEGIC PLAN (UPC-RSP) is to establish a roadmap to achieve results of qualitative and quantitative improvement that exceed the current activity in activities, in collaboration with the environment, understanding the university as a central system, which is able to respond from the point of view of demand or needs.

Consolidating an environment of research, transfer, innovation and relationship with the productive fabric and society in general (quadruple helix), so that the maximum mutual collaboration is generated, taking advantage of all the present capacities and potentialities that exist in the UPC, with intensive ecosystems in knowledge and innovation by differentiated strategic areas and multidisciplinary fields, able to generate answer to the needs and social challenges that are raised.

The UPC-RPS are focused on four strategic aims:

- KNOWLEDGE: boosting the cutting-edge research.
- TALENT: fostering the best careers.
- MARKET: providing solutions.
- INFRASTRUCTURE: investing for best science.

4. UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA (ULISBOA)

Maintain and reinforce the position of ULISBOA as a leading research University.

- Develop support structures and mechanisms that lead to increased participation in internationally-funded large-scale projects, with special focus on cutting-edge subjects and cross-disciplinary areas.
- Invest in renewed infrastructure that supports specific areas with a strong experimental component, to be financed by a more diversified funding structure.
- Maintain and reinforce of existing evaluation and assessment processes of researchers and units, with a more complete coverage of the scientific, technological and technology transfer components.
- Maintain and reinforce the link between research and teaching activities

5. AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR (AALTO)

Aalto University has a total of 7 key research areas: 4 core competences (ICT, Materials, Arts and Design, Business), together with 3 focus areas on grand challenges (Advanced Energy Solutions; Living Environment, Health):

- ICT <https://www.aalto.fi/en/research-art/ict-and-digitalisation>. Research in ICT and digitalisation relates to both theory and practice: computational and mathematical sciences, software and hardware technologies, secure communications, digital media, services, and engineering and management across technologies and industrial sectors. Focus areas are: Big data, Artificial intelligence, Software, business and cybersecurity, Digital services, 5G and telecommunications, Industrial Internet.
- Materials <https://www.aalto.fi/en/research-art/materials-and-sustainable-use-of-natural-resources>. Research contributes to diverse applications in ICT, energy and health technologies, textile design for fashion industry, bio-based product and arts design, and many other areas of industry. 17.8% of our publications belong to the most cited 10% in the world (Top 10 = 17.8%); Aalto hosts two Academy of Finland Centres of Excellence and over ten ongoing ERC grants related to materials research. Focus areas are: performance and design of materials, condensed-matter and materials physics, nanotechnology, bio-based materials, and mechanics, sustainable use of natural resources.
- Arts and Design <https://www.aalto.fi/en/research-art/arts-and-design-knowledge-building>. Artistic and design activities closely linked to research carried out in technical fields: art-based researchers focus on use of technologies within art and other socio-cultural contexts. Art and design knowledge-building activities include technology-based actions related to systems design and sustainable development. Focus areas are: Arts, design and architecture, Human experience, including customer experience, Industrial processes and service design, Data-driven experimental design, Cognitive systems, Organizations and teams, Creativity and creative practices.
- Business <https://www.aalto.fi/en/research-art/global-business-dynamics>. Research related to global economy dynamics is carried out in the areas of business, economics, and industrial engineering and management. Phenomena such as digitalisation and platform economy transform how we work, live and handle money and property. Aalto University research addresses a range of issues related to the dynamics of a global economy and is carried out in the areas of business, economics, and industrial engineering and management. Much of the work is done in close collaboration with Finnish industry.

Research on the Grand Challenges

- Advanced energy solutions <https://www.aalto.fi/en/research-art/advanced-energy-solutions>. Main research foci in energy research are energy sciences, multidisciplinary energy technologies, sustainable energy solutions. Research in these fields includes advanced and renewable energy technologies: efficient, eco-friendly, reliable energy production systems, distribution and use & monitoring and understanding people's environments. Results of energy-related research contribute to Finland's energy policy and have global outreach through sustainable energy solutions and wide range of energy innovations and applications. Focus areas are: Sustainable energy production, Energy storage conversion, Power engineering, Energy in built environments, Energy systems and resource economics

- Living Environment <https://www.aalto.fi/en/research-art/human-centred-living-environments> Human-centered living environments aims to understand how individuals experience their physical environment and how art, spaces, buildings, and communities can enhance this experience. The challenges of urbanization, efficient use of resources, changes in population structure, the opportunities offered by digitalization, business services and the experience of nature, are all included in this multi-dimensional research. With our recently opened Living+ Hub, we offer these actors a place to meet, exchange ideas and collaborate.
- Health <https://www.aalto.fi/en/research-art/health-and-wellbeing>. Research mostly focuses on neuroscience and neurotechnology, functional magnetic imaging, biomedical engineering, bioinformatics and computational medicine, as well as on health and wellbeing technologies and management. Focus areas are: biomedical engineering, neuroscience, biomaterials, digital health, health management and design.

Research is done in close collaboration with the University of Helsinki and Helsinki University Hospital. Their expertise in medical science and clinical research complements our primarily technology-oriented approach.

6. KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN (KTH)

KTH is one of Europe's leading research universities in environmental science and sustainable development. The wide spectrum of research at KTH demands variation in focus, approach and formation. We work to create an open atmosphere and break down traditional barriers between academic disciplines. Basic research is conducted in parallel with applied research, and the same is true of multidisciplinary work and specifically targeted work. Based on strong areas of research at KTH, six focus areas have been created. These work as platforms for multidisciplinary research.

- The **KTH Digitalization Platform** connects over 34 research groups and 19 competence centres in six thematic research areas related to digitalization issues: Data Analytics, Machine Learning and AI; Software and High Performance Computing; Digitalising Society, Human and Machine Interaction and Design; Communications; Control, Robotics and Embedded Systems; Security, Privacy and Trust...
- **KTH's Energy Platform** connects more than 450 researchers in 30 research groups and five competence centres in 17 research areas related to energy issues: Storage; Bioenergy and Waste; CO₂ Capture and Storage; Electric and Hybrid Vehicles; Fusion; Sustainable Architecture; Heat Pumping Technologies; Heat Transfer and Fluid Dynamics; Hydrogen and Fuel Cells; Hydropower; Materials; Nuclear Power; Solar Power; System, Policies and Energy Studies; Transmission and Distribution; Turbomachinery; Wind Power
- The **Industrial Transformation Platform** has divided the research into four overarching research areas: Product Development, Production, Business Models and Enabling Technology.
- The **KTH Life Science Technology Platform** connects seven thematic research areas that mostly concerns human health and the healthcare system, but also adjacent areas, e.g. environment and sustainability. The common denominator of all research is the contribution to human wellbeing: Bioimaging; Biomolecular Tools and Biomaterials; Infrastructure in Health; Mathematical and Computational Sciences; Medical devices; MicroNanoBio; Fundamental Research in Life Science

- The **KTH Materials Platform** connects more than 1000 researchers in over 80 research groups and around 26 competence centres in six thematic areas related to materials issues: Polymer materials - bio-based, synthetic and hybrids; Emerging materials - quantum materials, plasmonics, magnonics, HT superconductors; Materials for energy applications - storage, transmission, photovoltaics, catalysis; Sustainable materials - recycling, purification, design for circularity; Engineering materials - 3D printing, construction, alloys, infrastructure; Materials for information and communication technologies - photonics, thin films, silicon based technologies, magnetic material-
- The **Transport Platform** connects more than 800 researchers in over 40 research groups and 14 centres in five thematic research areas related to transport issues: Holistic Transport System; Future Transportation Infrastructure; Innovative Vehicle Concepts; Policy and Institutional Frameworks; Transport in the Information Age

7. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DARMSTADT (TUDa)

Bundling research in the three large, interdisciplinary fields Information and Intelligence (I + I), Energy and Environment (E + E) and Matter and Materials (M + M), that create spaces for interaction and synergies

- Strengthening of reputation and visibility
- Leveraging synergies interdisciplinary and across departmental boundaries in promotion of early career researchers and in promotion of research infrastructures
- Strengthening research in profile areas towards excellence and collaborative research
- Strengthening research collaborations inside RMU (RHINE-MAIN UNIVERSITIES alliance), with non-university research institutions and inside Unite!
- Profile areas within the three research fields Information and Intelligence (I + I), Energy and Environment (E + E), and Matter and Materials (M + M):
- I + I: Artificial Intelligence, Cognitive Science, Complex Interconnected Systems, and Cybersecurity & Privacy,
- E + E: Carbon-Neutral Circles, Integrated Energy Systems, Scalable Clean Water Cycles, and Thermo-Fluids and Interfacial Phenomena,
- M + M: Materials Design for Circularity, Nuclear Science, Synthetic Biology, and Intelligent, sustainable value creation networks for Industry 4.0 of the future.

Actions undertaken/foreseen to develop the Strategic Plan priorities .

1. POLITECNICO DI TORINO (POLITO)

- Action 1: Support scientific research by increasing doctoral candidates by 50%. The number of enrolled PhD students is ramping from 700 in 2018 to 960 in 2021. Incentives, such as multiple calls per year and early grants for covering the gap between the calls, were in place before 2018 and are a key to the success of our doctorate program. Since 2018, the local stakeholders (foundations and companies) supported an increasing number of PhD positions.

- Action 2: A university database of research for quick, effective and transparent mapping of our competencies. The RM (Research Management) project of POLITO regards the creation of an IT tool to systemize data coming from multiple sources and databases related to the research carried out in the University and to make them accessible through keywords. The project involves the acquisition and the use of the IRIS-RM web application for the registration of further data, not yet tracked, relating to the skills of research staff, laboratories, research groups, equipment, public engagement initiatives etc.
- Action 3: To increase the self-financing capacity by 50%. POLITO promotes the self-financing increase by means of several actions:
 - Actions aimed at making open access IRs operational and visible in the territorial, national and international context.
 - Development of an innovative model for strategic relationships with companies
 - Promote the participation in Horizon Europe by means of internal dedicated projects
 - Technology Platforms: environments for gathering all resources and optimizing their visibility and successful exploitation.
 - Facilitate and coordinate relations with external stakeholders, public and private, including large, small and medium-sized enterprises, both national and international. Matching between their needs and the skills of the research groups
- Action 4: Attract talented faculty members with complementary competences. POLITO promotes high quality research and the talent of researchers through internal calls for proposals
- Action 5: To promote the aggregation of single researchers and research groups, also at an interdepartmental level, on curiosity driven projects, as well as on research topics of great visibility and impact still unexplored in our university. Ad hoc support provided by the Research Support Dept to Interdepartmental centers and to Platforms on funding opportunities.
- Action 6: To orient interdisciplinary research towards the achievement of the sustainable development goals of the UN 2030 agenda. In the field of Research, the scientific production of the last three years has been classified according to the 17 SDGs. Research products of the last three years (more than 13.000 products) were analysed according to three different knowledge inputs:
 1. definitions and description of each SDG
 2. abstract of five publications identified as the more pertinent to each SDG (according to Google Scholar)
 3. SDG definition and pertinent publications selected by Green team members. More than 1.000 products, which were identified with the same SDG by the three different attempts.

In addition, an internal survey about the level of knowledge and awareness of the PoliTO community (first-year students and academic and administrative staff) in relation to SDGs has been administered.

2. INSTITUT POLYTECHNIQUE DE GRENOBLE (INP GRENOBLE)

Our laboratories are working to solve the major challenges and transitions of the 21st century in four key fields: digital world, industry: globalization and innovation, energy and environment

- Our researches focus on environment and eco-efficient production, micro-nano-technologies and – electronics, renewable energy, materials, digital sciences and management

- Development of Grenoble INP's Green Plan with indicators on the number of research projects linked to societal issues, sustainable development and social responsibility
- Incentive schemes: Funding of scientific equipments, local multidisciplinary projects, invited Professors, Conferences, and PhD grants from INP Presidency
- Reduction of teaching load and bonus for R&I project
- Strong involvement in Pôles de compétitivité with Industrial partners, regional Institutes and excellence Laboratories, regional, national and European Research Infrastructures and Ecosystems (EITs, Associations, Platforms, SRA Committees, etc.).

3. UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA (UPC)

KNOWLEDGE

- **ACTION 1: Encourage the participation of our Faculty in recognized programs of excellence**
Generate a support structure that allows participation in competitive programs of excellence.
Highlight and make visible the UPC programs of recognition of existing excellence.
- **ACTION 2: Encourage research lines with the greatest social, economic and technological impact**
Identify the lines of research with the greatest social, economic and technological impact. Search relationships and synergies with related sectors.
Establish a recognition award to the lines of research with more social, economic and technological impact.
- **ACTION 3: To give the maximum visibility internally and in the national and international scopes of scientific production**
Promote that the evaluation and evaluation of research is based on a strategic vision of research at the UPC, which considers both scientific and social impact, and which combine quantitative and qualitative methods, considering the diversity of disciplines and the diversity of academic profiles.
Promote open access policies to science. Increase scientific production by open.
Increase the positioning in the world reference rankings, both of the institution as well as academic fields and disciplines.
- **ACTION 4: Orient the activity towards new international technological trends**
Create an observatory for the prospection and identification of technological trends.
Create a map in which the specialties and abilities of the UPC research groups can be identified and visualized. Orient and incentive according to own capacities, technological tendencies and financing opportunities.

TALENT

- **ACTION 5: Attract talent to participate in our research groups**
Implement talent promotion programs that promote gender equality in research groups and centers.
Implement a fundraising plan to offer a scholarship program training of research staff, to capture and retain young talent.
- **ACTION 6: Encourage the international mobility of Faculty and PhD students**
Encourage the participation of the PDI in international exchange and mobility programs.

Encourage alliances that allow improve technology transfer through the participation and leadership of collaborative projects with other universities, centers of research and companies.

MARKET

- **ACTION 7: Encourage participation and leadership in new environments of technological innovation**

Design, implement and promote the UPC innovation ecosystem concept and design the incubation strategy, services and actions to promote companies present in the UPC (Innovation Hub) spaces. Define and implement the pre-incubation strategy Emprèn UPC, creative spaces in the different UPC innovation ecosystems.

- **ACTION 8: Strengthen the mechanisms for valuing technology and encouraging entrepreneurship**

Define a recognition model that encourages the transfer activity and innovation of UPC researchers. Design and implement a new intellectual property rights (IPR) strategy to detect, patent and commercially exploit technologies.

Redesign the UPC Entrepreneurship Program to increase the promotion of the entrepreneurial culture among students and UPC researchers and professors.

- **ACTION 9: Strengthen relations with the productive sector and the social environment**

Establish agreements with employers and cooperatives in the sector, especially small and medium-sized Catalan companies, to facilitate their development through the collaboration of the UPC in technology transfer and innovation. Design and implement a UPC - company technological challenge program.

Design and implement a plan for attracting and partnering with large companies towards UPC innovation ecosystems for the implementation of corporate venture and start-up scouting programs. Strengthen the collaboration with the productive fabric in the seven sectorial areas of reference (food, chemical, energy and resources, industrial systems, sustainable mobility, design, health and cultural industries).

- **ACTION 10: Promote the UPC's Center for Innovation and Technology (CIT - UPC) as a key instrument for the relationship and transfer of technology with companies and institutions**

INFRASTRUCTURE

- **ACTION 11: Adapt the scientific and technical infrastructures**

Consolidate support services where research, transfer and innovation come together, and the relationship with the productive fabric and society in general (quadruple helix).

Carry out an inventory, classification and compute the cost for using the facilities and equipment UPC scientists who can be used by companies and external entities.

- **ACTION 12: Adapt the support and management structure and information systems to the needs**

Design and develop a sustainable and ad hoc model of support and management (human resources) and maintenance of scientific equipment derived from new activities of innovation and technology transfer projects, making the most of the use of new technologies of information and process improvement.

The UPC –RPS also focus on a few thematic areas, those in which our current and potential capacities make us lead cutting-edge research: ENERGY, INDUSTRY 4.0, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

4. UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA (ULISBOA)

- Hire the best talent internationally, through a clear and attractive career path.
- Search for the best national and international partnerships.
- Search for diverse partners – Universities, Research, Industry
- Foster in-house support to Research, both pre- and post-award
- Search for diverse financing sources for Science, both national and international
- Lobbying for appropriate Science policies

5. AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR (AALTO)

– Attracting and fostering talent:

Attract world-class talent with our research infrastructures and the Nordic – safe, open and low-hierarchical -- way of life. Recruitment based on proven or potential disciplinary excellence and impact:

- Sustainability: World-class clusters of excellence in key research areas; complementary talent work on grand challenges
- Creativity: Generate novel ideas that can tackle grand societal challenges
- Entrepreneurial mindset: High-impact breakthroughs; strong industrial and societal collaboration, strategic company partnerships, placement of doctoral graduates.

– Developing selected infrastructures

Competitive infrastructures in key research areas; prioritized resourcing. Large infrastructures developed at university level, smaller infrastructures by Schools and Departments.

Sustainability: Infrastructures support United Nation's sustainability goals. (FAIR) data sets constitute infrastructure and support sustainability goals.

Creativity: Infrastructures serve as meeting points to foster radical creativity.

Entrepreneurial mindset: Openly accessible (some with fees) infrastructures available to our researchers, students and stakeholders

– New collaboration across fields

Centers stem from grass-root activities supported by department or School level. They can be established where needed, as short-term investments with mid-term evaluations, support collaboration of people from different fields. They comprise well-known clusters of excellence in their fields. Multidisciplinary platform activities in the 7 key research areas bring people together to solve grand challenges. Mode of operation is light-weight, supporting networking and serving as a well-known contact point. It initiates activities resulting in joint projects and publications.

– Cultivating an environment of innovation

An academic culture and working environment that enable creative, innovation-oriented research with focus on sustainable development. Acknowledge and incentivize, help international faculty to adapt to Finnish society, provide faculty with connections to Finnish business sector. Enhance entrepreneurial mindset among researchers and students; mechanisms for bringing together different actors within the

innovation ecosystem. Digital Aalto will enable an agile follow-up of innovation and commercialization activities. Support the creation of student-driven spin-offs.

– **Developing global and local networks**

Tackle the big global challenges with focus on sustainable development together with academic community and its active, high-level, global network of universities, corporations and innovation ecosystem partners. Active dialogue with stakeholders, sharing knowledge, building mutual understanding, enhancing impact of research and education in society. Develop university partner network and collaboration with companies to enhance quality of research, education and employability of students. Engaged community of alumni participate in the university's activities.

We communicate actively about collaboration with our partners, our diverse start-up activities and student-led entrepreneurial community as well as our radically creative, multidisciplinary research ecosystem.

6. KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN (KTH)

Each research platform has developed a strategic plan addressing the following objectives:

– **Catalyse multidisciplinary research activities**

The objective is to facilitate and enable collaboration between KTH researchers, centres, EIT-KIC's, research infrastructures and strategic research initiatives by providing arenas for collaboration and interaction beyond the conventional channels of the linear organisation, and across schools and departments.

– **Build and maintain internal relations**

The objective is to build and maintain internal relations across schools, departments, centres, EIT-KIC's, research infrastructures and other strategic initiatives in order to coordinate and provide strategic input from the focus area to KTH's management.

– **Enhance external visibility and recognition**

The objective is to create and maintain strong lasting relations with relevant external partners in order to establish KTH as a natural strategic partner, increase KTH's impact on society and industry within the focus area and to increase participation in decision-making bodies and strategic groups (on a regional, national and international level).

7. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DARMSTADT (TUDa)

With reference to Unite!:

- We increase the share of EU third-party funding. => UNITE.H2020 Obj 1 / WP2
- We continue to develop our well-known HIGHEST brand and use it to strengthen start-up and transfer activities from the TU. => UNITE.H2020 Obj 3/ WP4
- We support research on science communication at our TU and implement the results in the communication of our own research achievements. => UNITE.H2020 Obj 3/ WP4
- Structured doctoral programs (DFG graduate colleges, TU's own graduate schools, international graduate schools within Unite!, ITNs) are integrated into our research profile. => UNITE.H2020 Obj 4 / WP5
- We identify core facilities, i.e., facilities and instruments that are indispensable for many different research areas, and develop concepts to use them jointly. => UNITE.H2020 partially Obj2 / WP3

Stakeholders' list

Selected stakeholders from society and business have been identified, provided by WP4 (business), WP7 (society) and with input also from WP9 (dissemination) as the ones that could be able to provide input to the Alliance, foreseeing the added value of the Alliance respect to the sum of the partners. These stakeholders will be considered as members of the UNITE.H2020 Stakeholders Forum (SF), an external and independent body providing high-level advice to the UNITE.H2020 outputs' development. The SF will be created after the first year of UNITE.H2020 activities to evaluate and review the development of UNITE.H2020 in terms of global impact of the project activities on SDGs and societal challenges. The stakeholders could also be involved in the development of pilots in the last phase of the UNITE.H2020 project.

List of stakeholders

1. POLITECNICO DI TORINO (POLITO)

	Scope of the partnership	Target group	Related SDGs
Università degli Studi di Torino	<p>The University of Turin is one of the most ancient and prestigious Italian Universities. Hosting over 79.000 students and with 120 buildings in different areas in Turin and in key places in Piedmont, the University of Turin can be considered as "city-within-a-city", promoting culture and producing research, innovation, training and employment.</p> <p>The collaboration between University of Turin and Turin Polytechnics concerns all the university missions: Teaching, Research and Third Mission. The two universities have an inter-university department, a joint doctorate, common initiatives for sustainability (Unitogo Unito Green office and Green Team Polito).</p> <p>Concerning the outreach initiatives, multiple events are jointly organized or participated, such as Just the woman I am, EU researcher's night, Biennale Democrazia, Biennale Tecnologia, initiatives about Gender in research, Open Science and many others</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University students • General public, • People interested in research and university sector, • Research organizations, School teachers and pupils. 	3,4,5,6,7,8,11,12,13,14,15
Compagnia di San Paolo	<p>Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo (FCSP) was established for philanthropic purposes, to promote cultural, civil and economic development, on the strength of its assets and heritage.</p> <p>The Foundation pursues three goals: Culture, People and Planet, which are in turn divided into 14 missions. The decision to adopt these three goals stems from FCSP's desire to align itself with the international shared framework of the United Nations, which established the 2030 Agenda in 2015, asking individual countries to adopt the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the associated 169 targets, as well as the whole philosophy that led to them being formulated.</p> <p>The collaboration between Compagnia di San Paolo and Politecnico di Torino is established through a three-years agreement. In the 2019-2021 period it concerns Research (enhancing the university participation in Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe Programs, creation of Thematic platforms); Teaching (promote innovation in teaching and mismatch between market needs and graduates competences); Technology transfer and Outreach/Public engagement initiatives.</p> <p>Concerning the last point, Compagnia is a partner of Politecnico di Torino in many initiatives, such as EU Researchers night, Biennale Tecnologia, Just the woman I am.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University students, • General public, people interested in research and university sector, • research organizations, • School teachers and pupils. • Families, • people with disabilities/difficult situations/poverty, • Communities 	1,2,3,4,5,8,10,11,17

LAVAZZA	<p>Lavazza established in Turin, Italy, in 1895, has been owned by the family of the same name for four generations. The company has six production sites and operates through associated companies and distributors in more than 140 countries. Today, through ongoing partnerships with an international network of universities and scientific research centers, Lavazza operates four platforms in this segment. In 1979 the company established the "Luigi Lavazza Centre for coffee research" which is "devoted to the study of espresso" and has evolved into the Lavazza Training Centre, a network of over 50 coffee schools worldwide, where 30 thousand people receive training each year.</p> <p>Among the activities promoted by the Lavazza Foundation, established in 2002, is the Tierra project which, in partnership with the Rainforest Alliance, performs research into achieving the "finest end product quality", with a focus on the living conditions of people in coffee producing countries.</p> <p>Politecnico di Torino and Lavazza cooperate in the framework of specific agreements in research field on topics such as circularity and sustainable issues applied to innovation, for example in the areas of packaging and the application of artificial intelligence.</p> <p>Lavazza is also often involved in events of Public Engagement such as Festival della Tecnologia and Biennale Tecnologia organized by Politecnico di Torino.</p> <p>During the last edition of Biennale Tecnologia for e.g. Lavazza brought its testimony on the key theme of integrating the circular economy and innovation for the competitiveness of businesses, illustrating the opportunities created by the constant dialogue between the academic and business world, to build together a sustainable future tailored of a rediscovered humanity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Students • People interested in research and university sector, • Research organizations, • Other private companies sector 	8,9,12,13,17
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2. INSTITUT POLYTECHNIQUE DE GRENOBLE (INP GRENOBLE)

	Scope of the partnership	Target group	Related SDGs
Agence d'Urbanisme (Urban Planning agency)	Sort of "Think tank" for city officials of the greater Grenoble area and Isère, the aim is to bridge the gap between academic research and practice on urban planning => the Urban Planning agency collects questions from city officials about urban planning, ecological and digital transitions, etc. and asks experts from the University's research structure "Territories and Networks" to organize conferences, round-table, workshops,...to bring their input on these issues and help city officials make decisions. Examples of topics: "Autonomous vehicles", "Digital solutions for the planet", "Challenges for French metropolitan areas", etc. Other activities include: setting up joint projects researchers/municipalities and sharing knowledge through the publication of books	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City officials, • Selected • Representatives from the greater Grenoble area and Isère département 	7,9,11,3
Theatre de l'Hexagone – Art Science Workshop	Partnership between CEA research lab and the theatre at the crossroads between arts and science: organization of scientific workshops and debates, artist residences in companies, exhibitions,...In 2021, the focus is on Artificial intelligence and sensorial immersion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public, • Theatre audience, artists and scientists 	9

3. UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA (UPC)

	Scope of the partnership	Target group	Related SDGs
Collegi d'Arquitectes de Catalunya (COAC)	The Architects' Association of Catalonia is an organization with 10.000 members architects across Catalonia. There are several collaborations between UPC and COAC, including training activities linked to the schools of architecture at UPC, and other collaborations. Both institutions work together, and also in partnership with several municipalities in Catalonia, in an accessibility mapathon, that aims to create interactive maps identifying spots with accessibility problems in the cities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students, • general public, • municipalities 	14, 10 Depending on activities and projects.

Municipality of Terrassa	Terrassa is a middle-sized city near Barcelona and hosts one of UPC's biggest campus. The municipality collaborates with the university in several initiatives, involving research, social outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public, • UPC students 	3,4,5,6,7,8,11,12,13,14,15
Fundació Formació i Treball	Formació i Treball is a nonprofit devoted to training and social and work insertion of people at risk of social exclusion. FiT is awarded for the management of restoration services in several UPC Campuses. As a part of its mission, FiT is committed to responsible consumption and collaborates with UPC in projects related to circular economy with educational impact: Menu for the planet, with an offer of vegan menus with low carbon footprint, prevention of waste in the restaurants and bars, and is a key partner in the "Recircula Challenge", an initiative of challenge based innovation and learning to search for innovative solutions to foster circular economy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students, • general public, • people at risk of exclusion 	12, 8, 13

4. UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA (ULISBOA)

	Scope of the partnership	Target group	Related SDGs
Lisbon Municipality (City Hall)	Regular strategic collaboration on education, research and innovation, with the mission to define and execute policies that promote the sustainable development of the Municipality in different areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens, • parish decision-makers, • entrepreneurs, • local companies, • civil society organizations 	3,4,7,8,9,11,12,13,17
ALER: Associação Lusófona de Energias Renováveis	ALER is a NGDO (Non-Governmental Organisation for Development) with the mission to promote renewable energies in Portuguese-speaking countries. The Association facilitates business opportunities by supporting the private sector and attracting financing and investment, by liaising with national and international authorities to create a favourable regulatory framework, and by coordinating all stakeholders, acting as a cooperation platform and the common voice of renewable energies in portuguese-speaking countries. In order to accomplish its most important mission of promoting RE in Portuguese-speaking countries, ALER presents its goals in three main axis: knowledge, capacity building and representation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation agencies, • companies, • SMEs, • entrepreneurs from the energy and energy-related sectors, • researchers • policy makers 	7,9,11
TagusPark and TecLabs (Innovation and Entrepreneurs hip	IST/ULisboa holds 12.6% of Taguspark shareholders. Taguspark's primary activity is the installation, development, promotion and management of the largest science and technology park in Portugal, as well as the provision of the support services required for its operation. It occupies a total area of 360 hectares, 150 of which are occupied by around 160 companies and 16,000 professionals who work at and visit the park daily. The "City of Knowledge", located in the Municipality of Oeiras (nearby Lisbon), offers an ecosystem unique in Portugal, bringing together companies, research centres and the local university. The quality of this interface allows Taguspark, organisations, entrepreneurs and startups to develop marketable solutions with export and internationalization potential. Likewise, Tec Labs is the hub for all technology-based entrepreneurship initiatives from the Faculty of Sciences and the University of Lisbon (https://teclabs.pt/en/).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens, • entrepreneurs, • SMEs, • students and researchers 	3,7,9,11,12

5. AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR (AALTO)

	Scope of the partnership	Target group	Related SDGs
City of Espoo	<p>Espoo and Aalto are cooperating on ways to build a more sustainable world both locally and globally. As part of the international leadership programme for forerunner cities, Espoo is committed to achieving the UN goals for sustainable development by 2025. Aalto University was the first university in Finland to commit to promoting these goals.</p> <p>Aalto University and Espoo are striving to develop more attractive environments for living, work, research, and teaching, as well as for culture and innovation. Another goal is to create a viable growth platform for entrepreneurship and business and to reinforce the attractiveness and staying power of the area among international specialists. Espoo and Aalto University want to inspire and encourage creativity and experimentation with new kinds of solutions in their communities.</p> <p>Espoo is Aalto's partner also in https://smartotaniemi.fi/ project, whose target groups are companies, research organizations and cities.</p>	<p>The cooperation contains themes related to research, education, health care, urban planning, construction, events, and service design.</p> <p>Espoo's general target groups are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • civil servants • companies • civil society • organizations • citizens 	Depending on the project
ABB	Aalto and ABB have joint research projects going on in areas such as the regulation of electric drives, electromechanics, power electronics, electric grids, telecommunications networks, and data networks (5G and applications), the internet of things project on the Aalto Industrial Internet Campus (AIIIC), marine technology, mechatronics, and process technology.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Students 	3,7,9,12,14
Neste	<p>In collaboration, Aalto University and Neste strive to find solutions to major global challenges by combining high-level research with leading industrial expertise.</p> <p>The collaboration strengthens sustainability driven growth areas that are important to Neste, such as renewable products and low-carbon solutions. At the same time, the expertise of the Finnish chemical industry in chemical technology, bioeconomy, circular economy and digitalisation is being developed.</p> <p>The research collaboration involves professors and postdoctoral researchers as well as doctoral and master's students from many Aalto University Schools. Research areas include polymer and chemical engineering, catalysis, combustion engine technology, process automation and artificial intelligence-based solutions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Students 	3,6,7,9,11,12,13
Nokia	<p>In 2018 Aalto University and Nokia signed a partnership agreement to strengthen research and co-operation in the fields of information and communications technology, artificial intelligence, business, and arts and design.</p> <p>There are currently close to 20 ongoing research projects involving professors, postdoctoral researchers, and doctoral and master's students from Aalto and Nokia. Represented fields include, for example, 5G technology, signal processing, antenna technologies, artificial intelligence, machine learning, Internet of Things, mobile cloud computing and advanced materials. Also, experts from Nokia are often seen as visiting lecturers at Aalto.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Students 	3,9,11,12
Saab	<p>In 2017, Aalto University and the defense and security company Saab concluded a ten-year collaboration contract with the aim of strengthening and deepening their research collaboration, especially in long-term sensor technology research.</p> <p>At the moment, there are over 10 research projects ongoing involving professors, postdoctoral researchers and doctoral and master's students from Aalto and Saab. Represented fields include e.g. cognitive systems, artificial intelligence, microwave</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Students 	3,9,11,12

	<p>and antenna technologies, hydroacoustics, space technology, and quantum technology.</p> <p>One of the forms of collaboration is the Industrial PhD doctoral programme funded by Saab. Five doctoral candidates from Aalto are currently participating in the programme. The candidates will complete their doctoral dissertation at Aalto while working in Saab's product development projects. The goal is to train at least 20 new PhD's during 10 years.</p>		
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6. KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN (KTH)

	Scope of the partnership	Target group	Related SDGs
Värmdö Municipality	<p>The collaboration between Värmdö and KTH (Architecture and the Building Environment) started in 2018 on the initiative of the Mayor of Värmdö. The purpose is to jointly develop competence, capacity and innovations to meet local and regional challenges around sustainable development with the Värmdö archipelago as basis for scientific and challenge-driven exploration. A trans- and interdisciplinary steering group of municipal officials and KTH researchers facilitate and coordinate a range of activities including student course work and externally funded joint projects.</p> <p>Strategic partnership on education, research and innovation. The aim of the collaboration is long-term and sustainable results and effects such as more jobs, new businesses, new products and services, better marine environment, safer water supply, improved community service and quality of life.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil servants, • Companies, • Civil society organizations, • Citizens, • Teachers, • Researchers, • Students 	6,8,9,11,14,17
KTH Södertälje Science Park & Science Week	<p>KTH Södertälje is situated south of Stockholm in an area with a strong connection to the manufacturing and production industry. The activities run by KTH are undergoing a major expansion in the form of new courses and a new research organization in the field of Sustainable Production.</p> <p>One of the partners is Södertälje municipality</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public, • People interested in research and university sector, • Research organizations, manufacturing sector, • SMEs. 	8,9,12,13
Vetenskap & Allmänhet (Science&Public)	<p>Swedish non-profit membership organization that works to promote dialogue and openness between researchers and the public.</p>	<p>Activities aimed at stimulating dialogue between researchers and the public in novel ways and in new arenas. These include co-creation workshops, science festivals (including Researchers' Night in Sweden), mass experiments, conferences, science cafés and competitions. Citizen science: VA coordinates an annual citizen science mass experiment, develops a Swedish citizen science portal and is a partner in the EU-Citizen Science project. VA is a member of ECSA (European Citizen Science Association).</p>	Depending on the activities and projects
KTH Södertälje Science Park & Science Week	<p>KTH Södertälje is situated south of Stockholm in an area with a strong connection to the manufacturing and production industry. The activities run by KTH are undergoing a major expansion in the form of new courses and a new research organization in the field of Sustainable Production.</p> <p>One of the partners is Södertälje municipality</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public, • people interested in research and university sector, • research organizations, • manufacturing sector, • SMEs. 	8, 9, 12, 13

7. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DARMSTADT (TUDa)

	Scope of the partnership	Target group	Related SDGs
Strategic Partners Merck AG & DB Netz AG	Merck: Developing responsible and sustainable solutions for the future of society and business is the common goal of Merck and Darmstadt Technical University. DB: Interdisciplinary research in a variety of thematic areas, Consolidation of cooperation in a wide range of research topics "Extended workbench" through scientific contributions and support in project work Positive effect on the employer image of DB Netz AG, its visibility and thus the recruitment of young talent; Use of the railway operations field established in Darmstadt, which is available as a research platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientists, • teachers, • researchers, • students 	7,9,11,12,17
Hessen Trade & Invest (HTAI)	economic promoters for Hessen (federal state), organize events, network	The Offer is aimed at innovation and technology-oriented companies from Hessen as well as Hessian companies that want to expand abroad or expand their foreign business	9,17
Schader Foundation	In addition to the three universities in Darmstadt and around 40,000 students, the various institutes and research-based companies also contribute to the identity of the City of Science Darmstadt. The heads of these institutions meet regularly at the invitation of the Schader Foundation for a round table.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public, • youth, • companies, • cities, • decision-makers, • scientists 	4, 10, 16

SWOT Analysis

Definitions

The SWOT analysis summarized in the figure below synthesizes the review of partners strategic plans and R&I strategies and is referred to the Alliance as a whole. This was drafted by Task and WP leaders UPC and PoliTO respectively, and then reviewed by all the partners.

The Strength and Weaknesses quadrants are intended as resources and limitations of the organization (the Alliance in this case) whereas the Opportunities and Threats quadrants refer to favourable and unfavourable situations in the organization's environment (the outside world). The figure synthesizes the four SWOT areas.

Insight and output of the analysis of the Analysis

The partners are well aligned towards the approach to UN SDGs, Open Science and the Horizon Europe FP.

All partners have multidisciplinary platforms or other research structures, which will foreseeably be central actors of the implementation of the common R&I agenda.

Key opportunities are that the Alliance becomes a stronger partner towards other Alliances (e.g EIT KICs), attract funds through the participation to EU FPs and become a reference for the European Commission and other policy makers in the selected areas of interest.

Dealing with weaknesses, the initial lack of alignment of the partners agendas, organizational models and priorities is the inevitable status quo. Moreover, the different emphasis of the partners towards EU competitive funding is another initial lack of homogeneity. In this respect, the Unite! E+ alliance is a fundamental ally.

One foreseeable threat is the risk of lack of coordination with EU alliances on the key areas of expertise.

Alignment of partners in the approach to international, EU, national and regional policies

As the SWOT analysis pointed out, collaboration among partners for new R&I project are a great opportunity for the whole Unite! Alliance. Therefore, an overview of the main funding instruments and European and national level has been provided, in relation to the R&I domains of interest for the UNITE.H2020 partners.

European Funding: Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation with a budget of €95.5 billion. It tackles climate change and other green deal challenges, helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth. The programme facilitates collaboration and strengthens the impact of research and innovation in developing, supporting and implementing EU policies while tackling global challenges. It supports creating and better disseminating excellent knowledge and technologies. It creates jobs, fully engages the EU's talent pool, boosts innovation and economic growth, promotes industrial competitiveness and optimises investment impact within a strengthened European Research Area.

The specific programme under Horizon Europe which are the most interesting for UNITE partners are in the clusters under the Pillar II and also on Pillar I (Research Infrastructures, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions) and Pillar III (EIC and EIT). Focusing on Green deal and on the thematic areas of common interest (Energy, Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence, and Materials), these are the clusters in Pillar II where it's mainly possible to find funding opportunities:

Cluster 4, addressing the following EC priorities:

- A Europe fit for the Digital Age – Competitiveness: for a European industry with global leadership in key areas, fully respecting planetary boundaries, and resonant with societal needs – in line with the renewed EU Industrial Policy Strategy; promoting an ecosystem of technology infrastructures, catering for industry, including SMEs and start-ups, establishing a European data ecosystem, in conjunction with the Digital Europe Programme;
- A stronger Europe in the world - Autonomy: ensure a secure, sustainable, responsibly-sourced supply of raw materials and increased autonomy in critical ones;
- A European Green Deal - climate-neutral, circular and clean industry: reducing energy consumption, decarbonise production processes, protect the environment and enable a circular economy;
- An Economy that Works for People – inclusiveness: not leaving anyone behind – and a human-centred approach in technology development, including AI.

Cluster 5, addressing the following EC priorities:

- technological, economic and societal transformations required to achieve climate neutrality, and ensuring a socially fair transition that does not leave any EU citizens or regions behind;
- better air quality, increased employment, social inclusion, sustainable resource management (including biodiversity), and reduced dependency on fossil fuels;
- development of a wide portfolio of cost-effective carbon-free alternatives for each GHG-emitting activity, based on often in combination with enhanced sector coupling, digitalisation and system integration.

National Funding and NRRP

The National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRP) are part of the Next Generation EU (NGEU) program, the 750-billion-euro package, about half of which made up of grants, agreed by the European Union in response to the pandemic crisis. The main component of the NGEU program is the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), which has a duration of six years, from 2021 to 2026, and a total size of 672.5 billion euros (312, 5 grants, the remaining 360 billion loans at subsidized rates). Some funding opportunities according to the national priorities described below shall be considered for future activities of the UNITE.H2020 project and in a broader perspective, of the Unite! Alliance.

Italy –Recovery and Resilience Plan

The Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) includes investments and a coherent package of reforms, to which resources are allocated through the Recovery and Resilience Device for 191.5 billion euros and through the Fund complementary law for 30.6 billion euros. An additional 26 billion has been allocated to the construction of specific works and to replenish the resources of the Development and Cohesion Fund by 2032. Overall, around 248 billion euros will be available. To these resources are added those made available by the REACT-EU program which, as required by EU legislation, are spent in the years 2021-2023. These are funds for an additional 13 billion.

The Plan is developed around three strategic axes shared at European level: digitization and innovation, ecological transition, social inclusion. This is an intervention that intends to repair the economic and social damage of the pandemic crisis, help resolve the structural weaknesses of the Italian economy, accompany the country on a path of ecological and environmental transition, and reduce territorial, generational and gender gaps.

The Plan develops along six missions, the following interesting for the UNITE Alliance.

- **"Digitization, Innovation, Competitiveness, Culture"**: allocates a total of 49.2 billion (of which 40.7 billion from the Recovery and Resilience Device and 8.5 from the Complementary Fund) with the aim of promoting the digital transformation of the country, support the innovation of the production system, and invest in two key sectors for Italy, tourism and culture.
- **"Green Revolution and Ecological Transition"**: allocates a total of 68.6 billion (59.3 billion from the RRF Device and 9.3 from the Fund) with the main objectives of improving the sustainability and resilience of the economic system and ensuring a fair and inclusive environmental transition.

- **"Infrastructure for Sustainable Mobility"**: with a total amount of 31.4 billion (25.1 billion from the RRF Device and 6.3 from the Fund). Its primary objective is the development of a modern, sustainable transport infrastructure extended to all areas of the country.

France

The French recovery plan is of 100 billion €. It covers the following domains:

- "Ecology and energy transition" pillar (30 billion €): It is divided into several areas, including low-carbon transport, decarbonization of industry and energy and research and development on green projects, development of hydrogen energy, energy renovation of buildings, more local food and the High Environmental Value certification of farmers;
- "Business competitiveness" pillar (34 billion €): It consists to support specially mid-size companies and SMEs, Future Investments Program for innovation, whose mission is to finance innovation and to allow the relocation of industries deemed strategic: agrifood, health and technology;
- "Territorial cohesion" pillar (36 billion €): It provides investment support to local authorities, as well as the continuation of the France Very High Speed Plan and the digital transformation of the state and companies, the youth employment plan, investments for hospitals, and culture sector.

Spain – R&D and Innovation National Strategy (RDINS)

The R&D and innovation and industry must be at the heart of the initiatives and approaches proposed by the national public and private sectors, and it is in this aspect that the RDINS has a very special impact on the need to bring science closer to the economic and social progress, to be at the service of the 2030 Agenda and the political priorities of the EU.

To achieve this objective, the Strategy will prioritize and respond to the challenges of the national strategic sectors in specific areas that will be key for the transfer of knowledge and the promotion of R & D and innovation in the Spanish business. The capillarity of the system will help mitigate the demographic challenge in our country, promoting the distribution of its agents and infrastructures throughout the national geography.

The National Strategic Sectors are:

1. **Health**: new therapies, precise diagnosis, cancer and aging, and special emphasis on infectious diseases.
2. **Culture, Creativity, and Inclusive Society**: genesis of the human being, cognition and language
3. **Security for Society**: inequality and migration; the market and its tensions; the protection of society and cybersecurity.
4. **Digital world, Industry, Space and Defense**: AI, next generation internet, robotics, physics, mathematics, communication networks
5. **Climate, energy and mobility**: climate change, decarbonisation, mobility and sustainability
6. **Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources and Environment**: from biodiversity to food use of the land and seas

R&D and Innovation National Strategy (RDINS)

Portugal

1. Funding for Research Units (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, FCT – Ministry for Science, Research and Higher Education, MCTES). This is a competitive, multi-annual funding program for research Units. Units can also form partnerships improving synergies in order to obtain Associate Laboratory status.
2. Research Projects (FCT-MCTES): competitive funding for projects in all areas.
3. Scientific Employment programs: These are intended for financing PhDs for Research, both directly to the beneficiaries (Individual) or through Research Units (Institutional).
4. PT2020 – EU regional funding for development. It is intended for innovation projects in partnerships with the private sector
5. H2020 – European Union funding for collaborative projects and ERC grant funding.

Finland

National public funding agencies will allocate a significant funding in 2021 and 2022 for promoting green and digital transition and partnerships.

1. Funding is targeted at research promoting green and digital 'twin' transition, both elements (green and digital) are needed: Research advancing carbon neutrality, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and digital technologies. All research fields are eligible. Applicants must be consortia, not individual institutions. Collaboration with the utilizers of research results (typically, companies) are required.
2. Funding for research infrastructures is also allocated. These can be
 - national or international research infrastructures (funded by Academy of Finland)
 - innovation infrastructures and experimental environments (funded by Business Finland)

Sweden

The Swedish Government's Research and Innovation Bill outlines the direction of Sweden's research policy over the next four years 2021-2024. The resources will increase considerably already next year to tackle major societal challenges and safeguard freedom of research. The aim is for Sweden to be one of the world's foremost research and innovation countries and a prominent knowledge nation. The appropriation will increase by SEK 3.4 billion (333M€) in 2021. The estimated investments in 2022, 2023 and 2024 are around SEK 3.2. billion (314M€), SEK 3.3 billion (323 M€) and SEK 3.75 billion (367 M€) respectively.

The Research and Innovation Bill focuses on five major societal challenges: climate and the environment, health and welfare, digital development, skills supply and working life, and a democratic and strong society.

Germany

The German recovery and resilience plan provides 28 billion € of which 90% fosters **green and digital transformation**. The plan consists of 40 measures in the six focus areas.

- (1) Climate policy and energy transformation
- (2) Digitalisation of the economy and infrastructure
- (3) Digitalisation of education
- (4) Strengthening social participation
- (5) Strengthening a pandemic-resilient health system
- (6) Modern administration and elimination of obstacles to investment.

The focus area Climate policy and energy transformation is financed with 12.5 billion € for climate-friendly mobility, climate-friendly renovation and construction, and innovative energy systems. The focus area Digitalisation of the economy and infrastructure is equipped with 6 billion € for digitalisation of the economy and data as the raw material of the future.

The German recovery and resilience plan includes projects of common European interest (IPCEI) initiated together with France. 0.75 billion euros are earmarked for the IPCEI Cloud and Data Processing and 1.5 billion euros each for the IPCEI Microelectronics and Communication Technologies and the IPCEI Hydrogen, with which Berlin and Paris want to promote the development of production and transport capacities for green hydrogen and the development of a European value chain.

The High-Tech Strategy 2025 of the Federal Government promotes research into issues that are relevant to the economy and society. The strategy focuses on the areas of 'Health and Care', 'Sustainability, Climate Protection and Energy', 'Mobility', 'Urban and Rural Areas', 'Safety and Security', and 'Economy and Work 4.0'. Together with the Federal States and the private sector, the Federal Government aspires at least 3.5 per cent of the gross domestic product (GDP) on research and development by 2025.

Conclusions

This document summarizes the outcomes of the work carried out during the first 6 months of the project, aimed at identifying **R&I challenges and convergences** of the partners universities in line with the mission statement of the Unite! European University Alliance. In other words, to identify commonalities among the diverse member universities in their strategic approach to be aligned with the European Commission, Member States and Regional and Municipal research agendas and help their respective research staff to tackle with the grand challenges of humankind.

As research universities, all the members of the alliance consider research together with **technology transfer and innovation**, as two important missions of their activity. Actually, all members of the consortium show an important contribution to the research activities in Europe according to the number and impact of their publications, **research projects funded in competitive calls and technology transfer activity together with innovation activities** like participation in the European Institute of Technology and participating spin-offs.

Analysis of the strategic plans of the different member universities regarding their approach to deal with R&D and innovation activities suggests similar patterns. All member universities include in their strategic plans a series of actions devoted to facilitate these activities, enhancing a culture of excellence including ethical attitudes, quality procedures operating in an **open environment**. Moreover, it is also commonly agreed upon research activities are externally funded. Consequently, some of the strategic actions are devoted to be aligned with the various funding agencies. The commonalities found in this analysis provide the ground to establish a solid starting point of shared interests and goals, offering the opportunity of a substantial leap to member universities.

A common theme all members include in their strategic planning regards actions to **attract talent** to their institutions. Ph.D. is commonly viewed as a key instrument to attract talent, so the diverse members have different strategies to increase the number of Ph.D. fellowships. Similarly, increasing the number of postdoc positions are viewed by some universities as a strategic approach to attract talent. In regard to the attraction of established researchers to be staff members, member universities have different strategies mostly constrained by local regulations and relative restrictions.

Enhancement of **multidisciplinary research** is also a topic of common interest. All members assume that breaking the silos of traditional disciplines is key to perform innovative research activity and to be better positioned to deal with the great societal challenges. Particular interest is to understand the institutional contribution to **deal with the UN SDGs**. For this purpose, member universities enhance interdisciplinary research through different organizational approaches like transversal platforms or research institutes that put together researchers of different fields to team and boost the opportunities of innovation. This also permits to be aligned with the policies and strategies of the funding agencies,

that incentivize the multi-disciplinary approach to innovation. Researchers will be helped in preparing proposals and applications and being more aware of competitive research calls and opportunities.

Member universities include in their strategic plans the enhancement of a fair play atmosphere in the knowledge creation process. Specifically, an ethical approach to undertake R&D activities in the framework of **open science** so that the outcome of the research is shared and easily reproducible by other researchers. Sharing raw data is also important since it opens the possibility to extract knowledge initially disregarded.

Member universities exhibit also a common interest in **servicing their societies**, not only addressing great societal challenges, but **making research activities reach the society**. Also in this line, members are important stakeholders in the respective regional developments both through talent attraction and through technology transfer and digitalization.

Another commonality found in the analysis of the strategic plans is the enhancement of an **entrepreneurial atmosphere in teaching and learning, as well as of the R&D activities**. Member universities devote important structural resources to chaperon entrepreneurs to develop their ideas and participate in the creation of spin-offs.

The analysis suggests that **member universities share common strategies to deal with the goal to enhance excellence research, as well as technology transfer and innovation activities**. The European University framework opens new opportunities and challenges. Working together permits sharing infrastructures, good practices as well as enhance mobility and in general, better organized to deal with the great societal challenges. In addition, the alliance provides an opportunity to have more visibility and impact. The alliance permits to show a unified voice within the diversity at the European level, representing a structure that goes beyond a local impact without losing it. Finally, the alliance represents the opportunity to be better aligned with the policies of the European Commission and become an agile and efficient ally.

Despite the opportunities brought by the alliance in the R&I area, there are multiple obstacles to overcome yet. Obviously one difficulty regards the balance between European vs. National priorities and funding resources. The ambition of the common R&I agenda of Unite.H2020 is that institutional reforms are undertaken with evidence to all participants of the impact of the alliance in facilitating the R&D activity.

Next steps

The outcome of the performed analysis and conclusions as well as highlighted in the SWOT analysis, pointed out a set of objectives on research and innovation that could lay the basis for the definition of a Common Research and Innovation Agenda, in particular:

RESEARCH

Objective R1: Enhancement of multidisciplinary research

Objective R2: Promotion of a culture of excellence

Objective R3: Research for society

Objective R4: Open Science for fair play atmosphere in the knowledge creation process

INNOVATION

Objective I1: Enhancement of an entrepreneurial atmosphere

Objective I2: Digital transformation

Specific actions will be discussed within each WP and among WPs, on how our European University will look like in 2030, so to define pilots for each objective in some selected areas.

ANNEX I

SURVEY ON STRATEGIC R&I PLAN OF THE UNITE.H2020 PARTNERS

Background

The following survey will be used to draft UNITE.H2020 WP2 first deliverable: D2.1 **UNITE!Challenges and Convergences Roadmap** (M8) and it will help identifying the research priorities and concrete action of each UNITE.H2020 partner university, in order to develop the following WP2 task 1:

a. Review of partners R&I strategic plans and query of stakeholders' input on Alliance R&I

Strategic plans of partner universities will be reviewed and synthesized to map the complementary strengths (and weaknesses) of the partners in the research and innovation dimension. Selected stakeholders from society and business will be identified in synergy with WP4 (business), WP7 (society) and WP9 (dissemination) as the ones giving key inputs to the Alliance, foreseeing the added value of the Alliance respect to the sum of the partners.

b. Alignment of partners in the approach to international, EU, national and regional policies

Review of the European Commission's priorities (i.e the Green Deal, H2020 societal challenges and missions), selected off EU roadmaps, partner country's national and regional priorities and engagement to 2027 and the emerging challenges related to the post-COVID new context. Identification of opportunities and threats, with a focus on shared R&I challenges linked to SDGs, in collaboration with WP7 (society).

c. Definition of a Roadmap on compelling global challenges of common interest

Considered the E+ alliance plan, the analysis of the partners' strategic plans, the EU, local and global policies and opportunities and the post pandemic scene, a roadmap will be defined to create convergence of the allies in multidisciplinary areas of R&I such as Energy, AI, Industry 4.0. The roadmap will be grounded into the infrastructural action plan of WP3.

Strategic R&I Plan Review

Strategic Plan research priorities of your university

(List **5-6 research priorities** and give a brief description of each one. Max 500 characters per bullet)

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Actions undertaken/foreseen to develop the Strategic Plan priorities (Key actions related to the above priorities. Max 500 characters per bullet)

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Connections between the SP research priorities and UNITE.H2020 activities

(How the SP links to UNITE. Where your SP can benefit from UNITE and being synergetic, in particular in the field of Energy, Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence, Green Deal. Max 500 characters per bullet)

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Partner approach to EU and National policies

Breakdown of research funding (% of funding, by source type)

Years 2015 - 2020:

National / Regional (%)

EU (%)

Private (%)

International (%)

Other (if applicable)

Research units types and architecture (max 500 characters per bullet)

((max 500 characters per bullet)(Describe the organization and activities of the Grant/Research Support offices in your university: central vs departmental level, support type, from scouting of opportunities to proposal writing, to managing the projects. Describe how your university incentivizes and supports the researchers towards a higher number of proposals and a higher rate of success))

Research Support Offices (max 500 characters per bullet)

(max 500 characters per bullet)(Describe the organization and activities of the Grant/Research Support offices in your university: central vs departmental level, support type, from scouting of opportunities to proposal writing, to managing the projects. Describe how your university incentivizes and supports the researchers towards a higher number of proposals and a higher rate of success)

Interdisciplinary Research

((max 500 characters per bullet)(How interdisciplinary research is fostered and which kind of incentives, if any, are granted in your university))

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Inter-University Collaboration

((max 500 characters per bullet)(List existing initiatives of collaboration of researchers, groups, infrastructures involving other universities, how they are supported by your university and how they are scalable to the Unite! Alliance)

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Bottom up actions for the definition of the research priorities

((max 500 characters per bullet)(Explain whether and how the researchers are involved in the process of research priorities design, and how we can involve them in Unite!)

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